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Estimation of CBCT imaging dose based on CT data for radiotherapy patients

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Introduction: Nowadays, IGRT is used daily for each patient, which in most cases involves the use of CBCT imaging for each radiotherapy fraction. The aim of the work was to estimation CBCT imaging dose before radiotherapy treatment, which can be done if the dose is estimated based on CT data.

Material and Methods: CBCT imaging dose estimation was performed by measuring CDBI and absorbed dose for each imaging protocol individually. The measurements were performed with ten CBCT protocols on Elekta Versa HD and Varian TrueBeam imaging systems. The CDBI was measured in homogeneous phantoms with an ionization chamber. The absorbed dose was measured in anthropomorphic phantoms with an ionization chamber. A correlation was established between these two types of measurements in order to estimate the dose of CBCT imaging based on patient dimensions from CT data. Z

Results: For patient with an effective head diameter of 17 cm, the estimated dose was 0.05 cGy, 0.5 cGy, 0.27 cGy and 0.13 cGy for Head&Neck, Head full, Head half down and Image Gently protocols, respectively. For patient with an effective thorax diameter of 27 cm, the estimated dose was 0.59 cGy and 0.77 cGy for Chest and Thorax protocols, respectively. For patient with an effective abdominal diameter of 26 cm, the estimated dose was 1.11 cGy, 1.39 cGy, 2.14 cGy and 4.65 cGy for Fast Pelvis, Fast Prostate, Pelvis and Large Pelvis protocols, respectively.

Conclusion: The assessment of CBCT imaging doses in this way enables the selection of an CBCT protocol well before the start of radiotherapy treatment. The use of CBT imaging allows better and safer radiotherapy

treatment for patients, however, the dose that the patient receives on that occasion must not be neglected, even though it is significantly lower than the prescribed dose to target.

Keywords: cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT), imaging dose, image-guided radiotherapy (IGRT)

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